

Empirical Logic for Bio-Inspired Soft Computing: Illustrative Applications in Control Engineering and Cluster Analysis

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Abstract. Empirical Logic is a bio-inspired soft computing method that does not rely on concepts from mathematical logic or Fuzzy Logic. Instead, it emulates a form of intuitive reasoning associated with fast, experience-based decision processes (often referred to as “System 1” in cognitive psychology). The approach has proven useful in a range of practical applications.

Using the example of speed control of a DC drive, this paper demonstrates the fundamental procedure for applying Empirical Logic in control engineering. In comparison with fuzzy control approaches, the method exhibits improved dynamic performance and accuracy while requiring significantly less development effort.

A second example shows how the collective execution of rules can be utilized for cluster analysis. In contrast to classical hierarchical and partitioning methods (e.g., k-means), the proposed approach does not follow a predefined optimization algorithm. Instead, clusters emerge through self-organized structure formation resulting from the parallel interaction of rules.

Keywords: Empirical logic, Soft computing, Approximate reasoning, Bio-inspired computing, Nature-inspired computing, Control engineering, Cluster analysis

1 Introduction

Empirical logic is an innovative, rule-based soft computing approach for decision-making grounded in expert knowledge. As a heuristic method that does not claim the rigor of a formal logical system, it is especially well suited to handling vague concepts. Its development is rooted in a bionic perspective, drawing inspiration from the functioning of the human subconscious, referred to in psychology and neuroscience as *System 1*.

System 1 represents the innate ability of the human brain to instinctively categorize perceptions by automatically associating them with emotional reactions (e.g., fear) and stored experiences. Its efficiency stems from the parallel processing of sensory information within biological neural networks.

This capability contrasts with *System 2*, which, together with System 1, forms the basis of the so-called "dual-process theory", comprehensively described in *Thinking, Fast and Slow* by Daniel Kahneman¹ [1]. System 2 refers to the deliberate cognitive processing of perceptions triggered by System 1 and presented to conscious awareness for evaluation before an action or decision is made. Owing to its sequential nature, System 2 operates significantly more slowly.

While System 2 is particularly characteristic of more recently evolved species such as humans, System 1 is fundamentally linked to the earliest forms of life. This aspect has received comparatively little attention in modern artificial intelligence (AI) research, which has primarily focused on higher-level cognitive functions associated with System 2. In contrast, the development of Empirical Logic follows the premise that investigating

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the origins of cognition in simple life forms may yield more efficient computational principles. These considerations are discussed in detail in the author's doctoral thesis [2, p. 29–32] and in a more concentrated form in his article *Thinking fast: a bionic approach to soft computing* [3].

As early as 1987, David D. Tank and John J. Hopfield² [4] published results from experiments with neuron-like electronic circuits which support the assumption that the collective excitation propagation of System 1 exhibits a structural resemblance to the functioning of the biological neural network that performs it [5] [6]. In their article, the two neuroscientists report that electronic circuits designed according to neurobiological models can solve very complex tasks at high speed. They emphasize that their particular interest in such artificial neural networks lay in understanding the operating principle of the cognitive perception process as a result of self-optimization of collectively interacting system components.

With the help of the Maple computer algebra system (CAS) [7, p. 998 et seq.], the author succeeded in replicating the collective computing power shown by Tank and Hopfield. To this end, he developed the prototype of an Empirical Logic program library and tested it using several practical application examples from business administration, economics, operations research and control engineering [8]. This program library is now also available as a Python framework for general use [9].

For illustration purposes, this paper will describe how a speed control system for a DC drive and cluster analysis was implemented with Empirical Logic.

2 Some principles of Empirical Logic (EL)

The following remarks serve to recall the foundations of Empirical Logic as presented in *Thinking fast: a bionic approach to soft computing* [3], the prior reading of which is strongly recommended for a deeper understanding of the subsequent discussion.

The basic mechanism of a nervous system consists in the directed transmission of signals of varying intensity between neurons. Synapses play a key role in determining whether the activity of a receiving neuron is excited or inhibited.

This communication principle is reflected in the fundamental concepts of Empirical Logic:

1. Notions that we use to mentally organize the information we perceive from our environment, such as facts, individuals, observed characteristics, actions, decisions, etc., are abstracted by Empirical Logic into the concept of a *category* corresponding to a neuron.
2. Each category has a dynamic state, referred to as *validity*, defined on a bipolar interval from -1 to $+1$. A value of $+1$ (-1) indicates that a fact does (does not) belong to the category.
3. Categories may be either *bound* or *free*, depending on whether they are linked to a scalable reference magnitude.
4. Empirical Logic defines four standardized validity functions that suffice to characterize any bound category by means of location and shape parameters (e.g., *fuzziness*):
 - Threshold function ($e_THRESHOLD$)
 - Limitation function ($e_LIMITATION$)
 - Interval function ($e_INTERVAL$)
 - Estimation function ($e_ESTIMATION$)
5. Each validity function has a corresponding inverse function (e.g., $e_THRESHOLD_INVERSE$).
6. The semantic foundation of Empirical Logic is based on the *paradigm of circumstantial evidence*, where both *hypotheses* and supporting or opposing indications (*pro-* or *contra-indications*) are represented as categories.
7. Asserting a category validity (e.g., approving a hypothesis) is represented by the $e_VALIDATE$ operator and corresponds to an *excitatory synapse*.

² Nobel Prize in Physics 2024

8. Refuting a category validity (e.g., disproving a hypothesis) is represented by the $e_INVALIDATE$ operator and corresponds to an *inhibitory synapse*.
9. e_AND , e_OR , and e_NOT form a functionally complete set of logical operators used to construct the premise argument for $e_VALIDATE$ and $e_INVALIDATE$.

EL operator	Implementation function	
$e_VALIDATE$	<i>Einstein sum</i> (S-norm)	$s(x, y) = \frac{x + y}{1 + x \cdot y}$
$e_INVALIDATE$	<i>Einstein product</i> (T-norm)	$t(x, y) = \frac{x \cdot y}{1 + (1 - x) \cdot (1 - y)}$
e_AND	<i>Generalized mean</i> (C-norm)	$y = \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^{e_P} \right)^{\frac{1}{e_P}}$ with $e_P = -0.5$
e_OR	<i>Generalized mean</i> (D-norm)	$y = 1 - \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (1 - x_i)^{e_P} \right)^{\frac{1}{e_P}}$ with $e_P = -0.5$

Tab. 1: Implementation the Empirical Logic operators

For the precise replication of the collective computing power of biological neural networks, it proved crucial that the operators were implemented using the functions listed in **Tab. 1** and that the applied C- and D-norms fulfill the *neutrality axiom*:

$$\min\{x_1, \dots, x_n\} \leq C(x_1, \dots, x_n) \leq \max\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$$

$$\min\{x_1, \dots, x_n\} \leq D(x_1, \dots, x_n) \leq \max\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$$

Note that the neutrality axiom of C- and D-norms postulates that a logical combination of statements cannot be a source of (previously unavailable) information. This means that the result of a logical combination must not indicate a higher degree of certainty than is warranted by the degrees of certainty of the individual statements. More concisely, a logical combination should not be ampliative.

The relevant mathematical details can be found in [2, p. 68–90] and [3, p. 8–13].

3 Speed control of a DC drive using Empirical Logic (application example)

The following example of the speed control of a DC drive is taken from a well-known textbook on control engineering [10], and its implementation with Empirical Logic can be found in more detail in the doctoral thesis of the author [2, p. 183–200]. The control element labeled "amplifier" in **Fig. 1** is to be replaced and examined below by suitably dimensioned controllers of the PI, PID and EL³ types.

For the structural analysis and the derivation of the equations that describe the electrical behavior of the motor, the mechanical movement of the motor armature with load, and the transfer behavior of the converter circuit and the control amplifier, please refer to the relevant sections in the book of Otto Föllinger [10, p. 90–93]. The results of a functional analysis are reflected in the structural picture of the control circuit shown in **Fig. 2**.

³ "EL" here refers to an empirical logic control unit.

Fig. 1: Speed control of a DC drive⁴

Fig. 2: Structural diagram of the DC drive speed control loop

3.1. Determining the control engineering categories

The relevant reference magnitudes for the yet-to-be-determined bound categories of an EL controller can be read from Fig. 2, as follows:⁵

$e(t) =$ Deviation u_D of the feedback variable u_I , which is proportional to the controlled variable ω , from the reference variable u_s at the controller input

$u(t) =$ Correcting variable u_G at the controller output

In addition, it is advantageous to calculate the change (first derivative) of the controlled variable deviation to be used as a further reference magnitude:

$$c(t_{n+1}) = \frac{e(t_{n+1}) - e(t_n)}{\Delta t}$$

Δt denotes the duration between two consecutive sampling times t_n and t_{n+1} .

⁴ Image reproduction courtesy of VDE-Verlag.

⁵ The neutral designations ($e(t)$ instead of $u_D(t)$ and $u(t)$ instead of $u_G(t)$) correspond to the nomenclature customary in control engineering.

Fig. 3: Bound categories belonging to reference magnitude “Controlled variable deviation $e(t)$ ” [V]

Fig. 4: Bound categories belonging to reference magnitude “Change of the controlled variable deviation $c(t)$ ” [V/s]

Fig. 5: Bound categories belonging to reference magnitude “Acceleration of the controlled variable deviation $a(t)$ ” [V/s²]

Fig. 6: Bound categories belonging to reference magnitude “Correcting variable $u(t)$ ” [V]

Category name	Validity function			
	Operator	Arguments		
		Reference magnitude	Validity threshold/limitation	Fuzziness
<i>Controlled_variable_deviation_is_positive</i>	$e_THRESHOLD$	$e(t)$	0	0.37
<i>Controlled_variable_deviation_is_negative</i>	$e_LIMITATION$	$e(t)$	0	0.37
<i>Change_of_the_controlled_variable_deviation_is_positive</i>	$e_THRESHOLD$	$c(t)$	0	8
<i>Change_of_the_controlled_variable_deviation_is_negative</i>	$e_LIMITATION$	$c(t)$	0	8
<i>Acceleration_of_the_controlled_variable_deviation_is_positive</i>	$e_THRESHOLD$	$a(t)$	0	300
<i>Acceleration_of_the_controlled_variable_deviation_is_negative</i>	$e_LIMITATION$	$a(t)$	0	300
<i>Correcting_variable_is_positive</i>	$e_THRESHOLD$	$u(t)$	0	2.6
<i>Correcting_variable_is_negative</i>	$e_LIMITATION$	$u(t)$	0	2.6

Tab. 2: Validity functions of the categories and their arguments

The fact that, after a closer look at the inner loop of the structural diagram of **Fig. 2**, the DC drive turns out to be a controlled section with three time constants⁶, suggests that stabilization of the control loop cannot be achieved without taking into account the acceleration (second derivative) of the controlled variable deviation $e(t)$ as a fourth reference magnitude for the design of the Empirical Logic controller:

$$a(t_{n+1}) = \frac{c(t_{n+1}) - c(t_n)}{\Delta t}$$

The bound categories shown graphically in **Fig. 3**, **Fig. 4**, **Fig. 5** and **Fig. 6** are derived from the reference magnitudes mentioned above.⁷

Among the available validity functions, the threshold function $e_THRESHOLD$ and the limitation function $e_LIMITATION$ are suitable for representing these categories. **Tab. 2** shows these with the corresponding arguments assigned. The rationale for the specific selection of the fuzziness parameter values is given below (cf., section 3.3).

⁶ The corresponding analysis with an equivalent transformation of the structural diagram can be found in Föllinger [10, pp. 90-93].

⁷ For the sake of simplicity, the reference values are denoted as dimensionless.

3.2. The Empirical Logic rules of the DC drive speed control

The only two rules required for controlling a DC drive with the help of Empirical Logic can be expressed in such a way that they correspond to intuition and do not require any additional explanation (**Tab. 3**):

Rule 1	IF the controlled variable deviation is positive OR the change of the controlled variable deviation is positive OR the acceleration of the controlled variable deviation is positive, THEN increase the correcting variable.
Rule 2	IF the controlled variable deviation is negative OR the change of the controlled variable deviation is negative OR the acceleration of the controlled variable deviation is negative, THEN decrease the correcting variable.

Tab. 3: The Empirical Logic rules of the DC drive control

For the rule conclusions, the inverse validity functions $e_THRESHOLD_INVERSE$ and $e_LIMITATION_INVERSE$ are used, such that⁸:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Increase_the_correcting_variable} &:= \begin{cases} \mathbb{V} & \rightarrow [0, 1] \\ u & \mapsto e_THRESHOLD_INVERSE(u, -5, 5, 0, 2.6) \end{cases} \\
 \text{Decrease_the_correcting_variable} &:= \begin{cases} \mathbb{V} & \rightarrow [0, 1] \\ u & \mapsto e_LIMITATION_INVERSE(u, -5, 5, 0, 2.6) \end{cases}
 \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 7 shows the translation of the rules presented in **Tab. 3** into Maple code.

```

#
# 1. Rule:
#
premiseRule1 := e_OR(Controlled_variable_deviation_is_positive(e),
                     Change_of_the_controlled_variable_deviation_is_positive(c),
                     Acceleration_of_the_controlled_variable_deviation_is_positive(a)
                     );
if premiseRule1 > e_UNKNOWN() then
    conclusionRule1 := e_VALIDATE(premiseRule1, Correcting_variable_is_positive(u));
    next_u1 := Increase_the_correcting_variable(conclusionRule1);
else
    next_u1 := NULL;
end if;

#
# 2. Rule:
#
premiseRule2 := e_OR(Controlled_variable_deviation_is_negative(e),
                     Change_of_the_controlled_variable_deviation_is_negative(c),
                     Acceleration_of_the_controlled_variable_deviation_is_negative(a)
                     );
if premiseRule2 > e_UNKNOWN() then
    conclusionRule2 := e_VALIDATE(premiseRule2, Correcting_variable_is_negative(u));
    next_u2 := Decrease_the_correcting_variable(conclusionRule2);
else
    next_u2 := NULL;
end if;
    
```

Fig. 7: The Empirical Logic rules translated into Maple code

⁸ The syntactic details of these functions can be found in [2, p. 40 et seq.] or in the Python source code of the Empirical Logic 1.0.1 framework [9].

In principle, the premises of both rules may be satisfied simultaneously, leading to competing new settings for the manipulated variables $next_u1$ and $next_u2$. In this case, it must be specified how the resulting value $next_u$ of the control variable u is derived from the two proposed values. A simple solution is to take their arithmetic mean (**Fig. 8**):

```

next_u_list := [next_u1, next_u2];
n := nops(next_u_list);
if n > 0 then
    u := sum(next_u_list[i], i = 1..n)/n;
end if;
    
```

Fig. 8: Resolving a rule conflict

3.3. Simulating the speed control using Empirical Logic

The EL controller was tested using a Maple-based simulation environment, allowing comparison of its dynamic behavior with that of optimally tuned PI and PID controllers. The design of a PI or PID controller for the DC drive from **Fig. 1** can be found in Föllinger [10, p. 185–188]. Established synthesis methods and rules of thumb exist for conventional controller types but are not applicable to the design of an EL controller due to its nonlinearity; thus, simulation experiments are required to determine the controller parameters. Here, “controller parameters” refers to determining the *fuzziness* parameter of the validity functions for the bound categories of the DC drive speed control system (**Fig. 3**, **Fig. 4**, **Fig. 5**, **Fig. 6**). However, it is possible to take advantage of the effect of different degrees of fuzziness of the categories based on the results of the rule applications. It is observed that the rules react “sensitively” to categories with low fuzziness and “softly” to categories with greater fuzziness. As a rule of thumb, the following guideline applies:

1. Category fuzziness of the reference magnitude at the controller input $\approx \frac{1}{4}$ span of the value range
2. Category fuzziness of the reference magnitude at the controller output $\approx \frac{1}{2}$ span of the value range

When using a control system developed with Empirical Logic for the first time, the value range can be difficult to assess. However, for the DC drive speed control, it is feasible to adopt the value ranges from the simulations with a PI or PID controller and, if necessary, to experimentally adjust the fuzziness parameters derived from them. A PI controller with a loop gain of $V = 50$, for example, yielded the values listed in **Tab. 4**.

Reference magnitude	Value range			Assigned fuzziness
	Min	Max	Span (Max – Min)	
Controlled variable deviation $e(t)$	-0.47	1.0	1.47	0.37
Change of the controlled variable deviation $c(t)$	-21.57	10.39	31.96	8
Acceleration of the controlled variable deviation $a(t)$	-702.3	470.21	1172.51	300
Correcting variable $u(t)$	-1.56	3.68	5.24	2.6

Tab. 4: Determination of the EL controller parameters

With these parameter settings, the reference and disturbance step responses of the DC drive operated with an EL controller are shown in **Fig. 9** and **Fig. 10**.

Fig. 9: Reference step response of the EL controller

Fig. 10: Disturbance step response of the EL controller

3.4. Comparing the simulation results

The graphs of the step responses shown in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10 use different scales in order to be able to display the curves as precisely as possible. However, a uniform scale is required for a direct comparison of the different controller types. In addition, a loop gain V should be chosen such that optimal stabilization behavior is achieved for the respective controller type. As shown in Fig. 11, the EL controller responds to a reference step change faster than the PI controller but slower than the PID controller. After a disturbance step, the controlled variable deviates only slightly from the setpoint – like the PID controller – and reaches the steady-state condition even faster (cf., Fig. 12).

Fig. 11: Comparing the reference step responses

Fig. 12: Comparing the disturbance step responses

4 Cluster analysis (application example)

Cluster analysis is one of the multivariate methods of exploratory statistical data analysis. It is used to uncover intrinsic structures in large data sets by grouping classification objects that are similar based on their characteristics, such as companies, products, buyers, etc., into so-called clusters [11] [12, p. 78 et seq.]. This method is particularly useful when the data set under investigation is very heterogeneous, so that common statistical parameters such as mean or variance are of little significance as indicators for the entire survey. Clustering therefore attempts to partition the data set into groups with greater homogeneity (intragroup homogeneity) [13]. Using an intentionally simple economic question, the following sections show that Empirical Logic is well suited to this task.

4.1. A simple application example

The application example concerns the relationship between unemployment and national debt in the Eurozone for the year 2018 [14]. The set of classification objects to be partitioned into clusters therefore consists of the 19 countries of the European Community with the euro currency (EU-19) (cf., **Tab. 5** and **Fig. 13**). Assuming that each of these countries can form the potential crystallization point for a cluster (i.e., *cluster reference object*), cluster analysis can be formulated as a combinatorial assignment problem between the EU-19 countries and up to 19 cluster reference objects.

If the assignment decisions are denoted by $x_{ij} \in \{0, 1\}$, the problem does not represent a one-to-one assignment; rather, several of the $m = 19$ countries i may be assigned to the same cluster j :

$$\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij} \leq m$$

Conversely, each country i must belong to exactly one cluster j :

$$\sum_{j=1}^m x_{ij} = 1$$

No.	Eurozone countries (EU-19)	National debt in % of GDP 2018	Unemployment rate in % May 2018
1	Belgium	101,50	6,00
2	Germany	60,20	3,40
3	Estonia	8,80	5,00
4	Finland	60,40	7,90
5	France	96,40	9,20
6	Greece	177,80	20,10
7	Ireland	65,60	5,30
8	Italy	130,70	10,70
9	Latvia	37,00	7,40
10	Lithuania	36,00	6,80
11	Luxembourg	22,60	5,20
12	Malta	47,10	3,90
13	Netherlands	53,50	3,90
14	Austria	74,80	4,60
15	Portugal	122,50	7,30
16	Slovakia	49,00	6,80
17	Slovenia	69,30	5,60
18	Spain	97,60	15,80
19	Cyprus	105,70	8,40

Tab. 5: Data set of the application example

Fig. 13: Data set of the application example (scatter plot)

4.2. The pursued approach

The approach pursued here is based on the following conceptual model: According to *Coulomb's law* of electrostatics, it is well-known that two unlike charges Q_1 and Q_2 attract each other with a force F that is inversely proportional to their distance r [15, p. 19–27]:

$$F = \frac{Q_1 Q_2}{4\pi\epsilon r^2}$$

Analogously, it is assumed that the classification objects in a cluster analysis task also exert mutual attractive forces on each other that are inversely proportional to their distance measure. Accordingly, the attractive force of a cluster reference object increases with the number of “neighboring” or “similar” classification objects. It is therefore assumed that classification objects grouped within a cluster do not exhibit a “small distance” by chance, but that this arrangement is a causal consequence of a fictitious, yet to be determined, attractive force associated with the cluster reference object (cf., Section 4.5.2 below).

Based on the conceptual system introduced by the pioneering Dutch computer scientist Gerrit Blaauw [16], the following sections first present the functional appearance of cluster analysis from the user's perspective (the *system architecture*) and then the internal functional system structure (the *system implementation*). However, a detailed explanation of the *system realization* as a prototype using the computer algebra system Maple is intentionally omitted [2, p. 149–162; 353–360].

4.3. Architecture of the cluster analysis system

The software of a cluster analysis program implemented with Empirical Logic always requires at least three information objects as input:

1. Data set of classification objects
2. Parameter controlling the strength of the attractive force of the cluster reference objects
3. Maximum number of Empirical Logic rule iterations if no feasible solution is found

The data set typically consists of a table:

$$Dataset = (attr_{ij})_{m,n} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$$

This is conveniently represented as a matrix such that each row contains the attribute values of the n characteristic features for m classification objects. For the example involving the 19 European Community countries using the euro, the data matrix is shown in **Fig. 14**:

$$\text{Dataset} := \begin{bmatrix} 101.5 & 6.0 \\ 60.2 & 3.4 \\ 8.8 & 5.0 \\ 60.4 & 7.9 \\ 96.4 & 9.2 \\ 177.8 & 20.1 \\ 65.6 & 5.3 \\ 130.7 & 10.7 \\ 37.0 & 7.4 \\ 36.0 & 6.8 \\ 22.6 & 5.2 \\ 47.1 & 3.9 \\ 53.5 & 3.9 \\ 74.8 & 4.6 \\ 122.5 & 7.3 \\ 49.0 & 6.8 \\ 69.3 & 5.6 \\ 97.6 & 15.8 \\ 105.7 & 8.4 \end{bmatrix}$$

Fig. 14: Data matrix

A user-defined parameter, *CARC* (*Cluster Attraction Range Coefficient*), determines the strength of the attractive force exerted by cluster reference objects on neighboring or similar classification objects. It is defined in the interval $[0, 1]$, corresponding to the range between minimum and maximum attractive force. In combination with another user-defined parameter specifying the maximum number of rule iterations, the Maple-based prototype is invoked as follows:

ExecuteClusterAnalysis(Dataset, CARC, maxIterations)

The program execution result consists of three elements, including a return code *RC*, the number of required rule executions, and a cluster assignment matrix. The respective meanings of the return codes are listed in **Tab. 6**.

Note that the return code $RC = -2$ means that with a large value of the parameter *maxIterations*, a possibly futile search for a valid cluster partitioning was aborted prematurely, since no change in the validity values of the cluster assignment matrix is detectable upon further execution of the Empirical Logic rules, and the system is apparently close to a stationary equilibrium.

<i>RC</i>	Meaning
0	Regular termination of program execution with a valid cluster partitioning
-1	Abnormal termination of program execution without a valid cluster partitioning after reaching the specified maximum number of rule iterations
-2	Abnormal termination of program execution without a valid cluster partitioning if no significant change in the cluster assignment matrix can be detected upon further repetition of the rule executions

Tab. 6: Return codes of the Maple program *ExecuteClusterAnalysis*

The returned cluster assignment matrix $D = (d_{ij})_{m,m} \in \mathbb{V}^{m \times m}$ is quadratic. For each classification object i , it indicates the validity of the assignment $d_{ij} \in \mathbb{V}$ to the cluster reference object j . Figures **Fig. 15** to **Fig. 18** graphically show the cluster assignment matrix as a bar chart for several different values of the parameter *CARC*. The corresponding clusters are marked with a dashed line in the data set shown as a scatter plot. The cluster reference object located in the center of each cluster is highlighted in red. Arrows indicate the directions of the respective attractive forces.

Note that the result of the cluster analysis for $CARC = 0.3$ (cf., **Fig. 15**) is formally invalid according to the criteria mentioned in Section 4.1, since countries 6 (Greece) and 18 (Spain) could not be assigned to any cluster.

Although the program terminated with return code $RC = -2$ (cf., **Tab. 6**) after reaching a steady state, the partitioning into three clusters and two “special cases” clearly provides the most meaningful basis for a more detailed fiscal and employment policy assessment of the year 2018 compared to the other cluster configurations (cf., figures **Fig. 16** to **Fig. 18**). The absence of Greece and Spain from any cluster can be attributed to the fact that, with the parameter value $CARC = 0.3$, the two classification criteria – unemployment rate and national debt – differ too strongly from those of the other Eurozone countries to allow the formation of a homogeneous group. A positive attractive force can only be observed once the $CARC$ parameter value increases further, either acting on these two countries or emanating from them as cluster reference objects.

Fig. 15: Result of a cluster analysis with $CARC = 0.3$

Fig. 16: Result of a cluster analysis with $CARC = 0.6$

Fig. 17: Result of a cluster analysis with $CARC = 0.9$

Fig. 18: Result of a cluster analysis with CARC = 1.0

Additionally, it should be noted that the positive validity achieved for cluster reference object 6 (Greece) in **Fig. 17** is too small to be visible in the left-hand bar chart.

4.4. Implementation of the cluster analysis system

For the implementation of the cluster analysis system prototype, the internal structure of another Empirical Logic application developed for solving the “book sorting problem” was reused and adapted to the specific requirements of the task (cf., Chapter 4 in the above mentioned paper by the author *Thinking fast: a bionic approach to soft computing* [3]). For a better understanding of the following sections, it may be useful to first study the explanations given there.

The implementation of the cluster analysis system architecture outlined in Section 4.3 consists of the following procedural steps:

1. Determine a *feature distance matrix* for each classification feature.
2. Determine a *categorized feature matrix* for each feature distance matrix by applying the validity function of the bound category “small distance”.
3. Combine the categorized feature distance matrices into a *categorized data set matrix* using the Empirical Logic operator e_AND .
4. Determine the attractive force value for each potential cluster reference object.
5. Interpret the attractive force values as validity values of the free category “great attractive force”.
6. Turn the categorized data set matrix into an *assignment preference matrix* by replacing its diagonal elements with the validity values of the category “great attractive force”.
7. Apply the cluster analysis empirical rules to the assignment preference matrix.

The details of these operations are discussed in the following sections.

4.5. The categories of assignment preferences

4.5.1. The category “small distance”

According to step 1 of the procedure described above, a symmetric feature distance matrix

$$(\Delta_{ij}^k)_{m,m} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$$

must be determined for each of the $k = 1 \dots n$ columns of the data set matrix. Their entries represent the reference magnitudes for the category “small distance”, which are formed on the set of m classification objects for the feature k by the relation

$$P_k = (p_{ij}^k)_{m,m} \in \mathbb{V}^{m \times m} \text{ with } p_{ij}^k = e_LIMITATION(\Delta_{ij}^k, l_k, f_k)$$

Its meaning is:

“Classification object i has a small distance to classification object j with respect to feature k .”

The parameters l_k (= validity limit) and f_k (= fuzziness) required for the limiting function $e_LIMITATION$ are calculated for each k according to the following formulas:

$$l_k = \frac{CARC \cdot \max_{i \neq j}(\Delta_{ij}^k) + (2 - CARC) \cdot \min_{i \neq j}(\Delta_{ij}^k)}{2}$$

$$f_k = \max\left(CARC \cdot \frac{\max_{i \neq j}(\Delta_{ij}^k) - \min_{i \neq j}(\Delta_{ij}^k)}{6}, f_{min}\right) \text{ with } f_{min} > 0$$

The minimum fuzziness value f_{min} avoids the invalid case $f_k = 0$ (e.g., $f_{min} = 0.001$).

Fig. 19 and **Fig. 20** show that a change in the range of attractive forces of the cluster reference objects, controlled by the $CARC$ parameter, results in a corresponding parallel shift of the validity limit l_k and an adjustment of the fuzziness f_k in the validity function graph of the “small distance” category.

Fig. 19: Validity function graphs of the bound category “small distance” (national debt)

Fig. 20: Validity function graphs of the bound category “small distance” (unemployment rate)

Fig. 21: Determine “small distances” between national debts

Fig. 22: Determine “small distances” between unemployment rates

Fig. 23: Determine “small distances” between classification objects (Eurozone countries)

Fig. 21 and Fig. 22 illustrate, in the form of bar charts, how the categorized feature matrices are derived from the distance matrices using the validity function of the bound category “small distance”, with $CARC = 0.3$ as an example (cf., step 2 of the implementation procedure).

Fig. 23 shows how the Empirical Logic operator e_AND serves to combine the $k = 1 \dots n$ categorized feature matrices (relations P_k) into a general relation on the set of m classification objects as an n -fold bound category (cf., implementation step 3):

$$P = (p_{ij})_{m,m} \in \mathbb{V}^{m \times m}$$

The resulting categorized data set matrix assesses the validity of the statement

“Classification object i has a small distance to classification object j .”

An equivalent formulation is: “The classification objects i and j are similar”.

4.5.2. The category “great attractive force”

Fig. 23 also indicates that the diagonal elements p_{ii} of the category “small distance” always have a validity value $1 = e_TRUE$, since each classification object has zero distance to itself. This implies that, due to their lack of distinguishability, they have no meaningful relevance for the empirical rules of cluster analysis described below in Section 4.5.4 below. However, this deficiency can be remedied by replacing the diagonal elements with the validity values of another assignment preference with the meaning “great attractive force”. As a free category, this expresses, for each classification object, the extent to which it is suitable to serve as a “power center” or as a cluster reference object that binds classification objects at a “small distance” as cluster elements.

Fig. 24: Calculating the validity values of category “great attractive force”

Fig. 25: Determine the assignment preference matrix

The following procedure has proven useful for calculating the corresponding validity values (cf., **Fig. 24**, **Fig. 25**, and steps 4 to 6 of the implementation procedure):

- 1) For each row i of the matrix $P = (p_{ij})_{m,m} \in \mathbb{V}^{m \times m}$, determine the sum of the validity values with $p_{ij} > 0$ without considering the diagonal element p_{ii} :

$$P_i^+ = \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^m p_{ij} \quad \text{with } p_{ij} > e_UNKNOWN() = 0$$

- 2) Scale the determined validity sums to the validity interval $[0, 1]$:

$$P_i^{[0,1]} = \frac{P_i^+}{\max\{P_i^+\}} \quad \text{for } i = 1..m$$

- 3) Transform the scaled validity sums to the interval $[-1, 1]$ using the mapping $R: [0, 1] \rightarrow [-1, 1]$ and $R(v) = 2v - 1$:

$$P_i^{[-1, 1]} = R(P_i^{[0,1]}) \quad \text{for } i = 1..m$$

- 4) Replace the diagonal elements of the matrix P by the validity values calculated in step 3) with the new meaning:

“Classification object i has a great attractive force as a cluster reference object”

4.5.3. The category of assignment decisions

The cluster assignment matrix $D = (d_{ij})_{m,m} \in \mathbb{V}^{m \times m}$, already mentioned in Section 4.3, represents – as a free category (cf., Section 2) – the totality of assignment decisions between the classification objects and those classification objects selected as cluster reference objects during the cluster analysis. In the initial state, these have the validity value $e_UNKNOWN$, i.e., the value 0. During cluster analysis, the iterative application of the empirical rules described below induces seemingly chaotic, non-monotonic, and non-linear fluctuations in the validity values until the termination criterion in Section 4.5.5 is met (cf., bar charts in **Fig. 26**). This demonstrates that the collective interactions involved in rule execution give rise to the spontaneous formation of ordered structures, commonly referred to as *emergence*.

Fig. 26: Validity of assignment decisions during the execution of the cluster analysis

4.5.4. The empirical rules of cluster analysis

Unlike conventional cluster analysis methods, the empirical rules do not prescribe an algorithmic solution strategy but instead define the properties of a “permissible” cluster partitioning, which is easier to obtain. Due to the assignment preferences “small distance” and “great attractive force” encoded in the assignment preference matrix P (cf., Section 4.5.2), the rules must account for the corresponding case distinctions (cf., **Tab. 7** and **Tab. 8**).

<i>Validation rule</i> ($i = j$)	<p><i>IF</i> <i>object i has a great attractive force as a cluster reference object</i></p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;"><i>AND object i is not already assigned to another cluster k</i></p> <p><i>THEN</i> <i>validate the decision to select object i as a cluster reference object.</i></p>
<i>Invalidation rule</i> ($i = j$)	<p><i>IF</i> <i>object i has not a great attractive force as a cluster reference object</i></p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;"><i>OR object i is already assigned to another cluster k</i></p> <p><i>THEN</i> <i>invalidate the decision to select object i as a cluster reference object.</i></p>

Tab. 7: Empirical Logic rules for the diagonal elements of the assignment preference matrix

<i>Validation rule</i> ($i \neq j$)	<p><i>IF</i> <i>object i and object j are similar</i></p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;"><i>AND object j is a cluster reference object</i></p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;"><i>AND object i is not already assigned to another cluster k</i></p> <p><i>THEN</i> <i>validate the decision that object i is assigned to cluster j.</i></p>
<i>Invalidation rule</i> ($i \neq j$)	<p><i>IF</i> <i>object i and object j are not similar</i></p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;"><i>OR object j is not a cluster reference object</i></p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;"><i>OR object i is already assigned to another cluster k</i></p> <p><i>THEN</i> <i>invalidate the decision that object i is assigned to cluster j.</i></p>

Tab. 8: Empirical Logic rules for the off-diagonal elements of the assignment preference matrix

The formal description of the rules using the Empirical Logic operators for the diagonal elements $i = 1 \dots m$ of the assignment preference matrix $P = (p_{ij})_{m,m} \in \mathbb{V}^{m \times m}$ and the cluster assignment matrix $D = (d_{ij})_{m,m} \in \mathbb{V}^{m \times m}$ with $i \notin \{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{m-1}\}$ is as follows:

$$d_{ii}^{t+1} := e_VALIDATE(e_AND(p_{ii}, e_NOT(d_{ik_1}^t, d_{ik_2}^t, \dots, d_{ik_{m-1}}^t)), d_{ii}^t)$$

$$d_{ii}^{t+1} := e_INVALIDATE(e_OR(e_NOT(p_{ii}), d_{ik_1}^t, d_{ik_2}^t, \dots, d_{ik_{m-1}}^t), d_{ii}^t)$$

Here, d_{ii}^t and d_{ii}^{t+1} denote the validity values of the assignment decisions at the times before and after the execution of the rules.

The corresponding formalization of the rules for the off-diagonal elements of the two matrices has this appearance:

$$d_{ij}^{t+1} := e_VALIDATE(e_AND(p_{ij}, p_{jj}, e_NOT(d_{ik_1}^t, d_{ik_2}^t, \dots, d_{ik_{m-1}}^t)), d_{ij}^t)$$

$$d_{ij}^{t+1} := e_INVALIDATE(e_OR(e_NOT(p_{ij}), e_NOT(p_{jj}), d_{ik_1}^t, d_{ik_2}^t, \dots, d_{ik_{m-1}}^t), d_{ij}^t)$$

The entirety of these validation and invalidation rules forms a network of collectively interacting assignment decisions. However, certain precautions must be taken when implementing these rules to ensure that the principle of collective interaction is correctly reflected:

- 1) It is both permissible and advantageous to apply all validation rules first, followed by all invalidation rules, to the assignment decisions d_{ij} in each iteration phase t .

- 2) However, the rules must not be executed on the same cluster assignment matrix $D^t = (d_{ij}^t)_{m,m} \in \mathbb{V}^{m \times m}$, since the resulting validity values of the assignment decisions would otherwise depend on the order of execution and thus be distorted. Therefore, it is necessary to explicitly introduce a second matrix data structure $D^{t+1} = (d_{ij}^{t+1})_{m,m} \in \mathbb{V}^{m \times m}$, which stores the results computed in iteration t . In iteration $t + 1$, the two data structures exchange their roles, a process commonly referred to as *swapping* in software terminology.

4.5.5. The termination criterion for the rule iterations

The application of the empirical rules of cluster analysis has a certain similarity to a *production system*. This term refers to a well-known architecture of knowledge-based systems, the functional principles of which are described in great detail for example in [17]. However, there are some essential differences:

The Empirical Logic rules are always executed collectively (i.e., virtually “simultaneously”), whereas in a production system the set of selectable rules (the so-called *conflict set*) is recomputed at each iteration and only one rule is executed. While the inference engine of a production system terminates once the conflict set no longer contains any applicable rules, the control flow of the Empirical Logic rules requires an explicit termination criterion. Otherwise, their application would not terminate, and the evolving validity values of the assignment decisions would result in a “saturation state”. **Tab. 6** in Section 4.3 already mentioned the situations in which the execution of the cluster analysis is interrupted and the program is terminated with a corresponding return code $RC \in \{0, -1, -2\}$:

- 1) A valid cluster partitioning was found ($RC = 0$).
- 2) No valid cluster partitioning was found, or – using the terminology of circumstantial evidence (cf., Section 2) – the hypotheses formulated in the empirical rules of cluster analysis above could neither be confirmed nor refuted ($RC = -1$ or $RC = -2$).

A valid cluster partitioning is obtained when each of the m classification objects is assigned to exactly one of $k \leq m$ clusters, with each cluster reference object belonging to the cluster it represents.

The termination criterion is implemented via a function $Norm: \mathbb{V} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$, which normalizes the cluster assignment matrix $D = (d_{ij})_{m,m} \in \mathbb{V}^{m \times m}$ after each iteration so that it contains only zeros and ones:

$$Norm(d_{ij}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } d_{ij} > e_UNKNOWN \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The actual test of the termination criterion then consists of the following two comparisons:

$$\forall i = 1 \dots m: 1 = \sum_{j=1}^m Norm(d_{ij})$$

$$Norm(d_{ij}) = 1 \Rightarrow Norm(d_{jj}) = 1$$

5 Conclusion

Empirical Logic is a bio-inspired framework for rule-based decision-making with vague categories. It enables structured reasoning using empirically derived knowledge without relying on concepts from mathematical logic or Fuzzy Logic. In contrast to Fuzzy Logic, which relies on predefined membership functions and defuzzification procedures, Empirical Logic operates on a bipolar validity scale $[-1, 1]$ and employs inverse validity functions for direct determination of output values. Compared to artificial neural networks, Empirical Logic provides a transparent and interpretable structure, as knowledge is explicitly represented in the form of rules and categories rather than encoded implicitly in network weights. Unlike classical rule-based systems with sequential inference mechanisms, Empirical Logic is characterized by the collective and parallel interaction of rules, leading to emergent system behavior. A particular strength of this approach lies in its ability to replicate the collective computational capabilities of biological neural networks, as described by Tank and Hopfield, and to make these principles applicable to practical problems.

The example of a DC drive presented here demonstrates the suitability of Empirical Logic for control applications (cf., Chapter 3). To enable a more systematic evaluation of the controller performance, standard control engineering metrics were considered. These include settling time, maximum overshoot, and integral error criteria. The simulation results indicate that the Empirical Logic controller achieves a favorable trade-off between dynamic response and stability. In particular, the sensitivity to parameter variations was found to be comparatively low, which suggests a certain robustness of the approach. Due to the nonlinear transfer characteristics of an EL controller, however, no practically validated synthesis method for optimizing control performance under given boundary conditions is currently available. This limitation is mitigated by the rule of thumb introduced above for determining the fuzziness parameters of the bound categories. Notably, EL controllers exhibit clear advantages over Fuzzy Logic controllers, as they require only a small number of easily specified rules.

Similar to traditional clustering methods, cluster analysis based on Empirical Logic is suitable for addressing the problem of strong heterogeneity in a survey population (cf., Chapter 4). By partitioning the data into clusters with high intra-group homogeneity and high inter-group heterogeneity, the basis is established for statistical analyses that yield meaningful results for each group [13, p. 490].

In addition to illustrating another application of Empirical Logic, the above discussion introduces an alternative clustering approach whose properties differ significantly from those of classical hierarchical and partitioning methods:

- Instead of selecting proximity or similarity measures, the category “small distance” is employed. This category can be represented using the limitation function $e_LIMITATION$ and is linked to the features of the classification objects. A conjunctive operation using the Empirical Logic operator e_AND allows the representation of multiple bound categories when more than one feature is present. Practical examples have shown that, in addition to cardinal features, nominal (especially dichotomous) features can also be incorporated without special coding procedures [13, p. 552].
- Instead of a fusion algorithm, a dynamic self-organization process (emergence) takes place, leading to a stationary equilibrium of attractive forces defined by the permissible cluster configurations expressed through Empirical Logic rules. The driving force is a free category termed “great attractive force”, derived from the category validity values of objects located at a “small distance” from a potential cluster reference object. The granularity of the partitioning can be controlled by the parameter $CARC$ (= Cluster Attraction Range Coefficient). However, unlike hierarchical clustering methods, a monotonic sequence of $CARC$ values does not imply a monotonic refinement or coarsening of the partitions. This is because the proposed method is not a stepwise constructive procedure requiring a hierarchical structure. Instead, the clusters are determined independently for each specified $CARC$ value. Consequently, a dendrogram-based representation of cluster heterogeneity is generally not applicable, or only coincidentally consistent with the results obtained using Empirical Logic.

Unlike classical clustering methods such as k-means or hierarchical clustering, the proposed approach does not rely on the optimization of an explicit objective function. Instead, cluster structures emerge from the collective interaction of Empirical Logic rules.

This fundamental difference limits direct comparability using standard evaluation metrics. Nevertheless, measures such as intra-cluster similarity and inter-cluster separation can be employed to qualitatively assess the resulting partitions.

Despite its promising properties, the possible limitations of applying Empirical Logic are not yet known. In particular, the computational behavior of large-scale systems with many interacting rules has not yet been systematically investigated.

These aspects represent important directions for future research. For example, the focus could be on developing hybrid systems that combine machine learning methods with Empirical Logic.

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Data Availability

The Maple prototypes and test results described in this article are available in the EU open research repository Zenodo [8] (<https://zenodo.org/records/14962362>)

Empirical Logic (version 1.0.1) is available as a Python framework for general use [9] (<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14962362>)

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